

Social Evil: Gender-Based Discrimination in the Agricultural Sector

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Abstract

In an agricultural country like India, the unorganized sector plays an important role in employment. As per the economic survey (2022-23), 47 percent population is dependent on agriculture. Especially women depend upon the agriculture sector for their livelihoods and on the other side agriculture depends upon women's labour. Most agricultural activities like harvesting, loading and unloading of products, storing products, packing of products, cotton picking, and collecting wood for fuel, are exclusively considered as women domain. Women a large part of the workforce despite this their role in economic development has been ignored and their status is considered very low. They don't have equal rights in their occupation as men and their choices are also limited to select an occupation, due to cultural, social, and economic constraints. Women face gender bias in the labour market. Women have fewer basic facilities like health, employment, and education as compared to men and they given less wages as compared to men for the same work. Especially in the unorganised sector the status of women is very pathetic and they are exploited at work. A labour-intensive country like India can develop at a rapid pace by preventing gender discrimination and making efficient use of women labourers.

Keywords

Agriculture, Gender discrimination, Female, Labour, Wages, Government.

Introduction

In an agricultural countries like India, the unorganised sector plays an important role in employment. As per the economic survey (2022-23), 47 per cent population is dependent on. In a highly populated country like India, the labour force plays an important role in the economic development of the country. In the agriculture sector, small and marginal farmers use labour-intensive techniques for production due to lack of capital. Most of the agricultural activities are carried out by labourers instead of machines because labour is a cheap factor as compared to capital. Women play an important role as labourers in this sector. Agricultural activities like sowing and harvesting, storage of the products, packing of products, and cotton picking are done exclusively by women labourers. The contribution of women who belong to marginal and small land holding families is greater compared to women of large land holding families. The status and living standard of large land holding families are high due to high agricultural income from crops. So, men and women from these families hire labourers in their fields and women do not go outside of the house for work. Women of these families with large holdings are engaged mostly in housework. Most agricultural activities performed by hired labourers, especially paddy planting is certainly not possible without women labourers. There is doubt that whether women belonging to the landlords or landless families, perform physically hard duties and still their labour goes unrecognised. Most agricultural activities like harvesting, storage of products, packing of products, cotton picking, and collecting wood for fuel, etc are carried out by women. Women spend long hours doing laundry, preparing food, looking after live stocks, collecting fuel and fodder, and taking care of children. As well inspite of working hard both at field and home, they are not given their due.

Female workers were 32.2 percent of total workers in 2004-05. Women are a large part of the workforce despite this their role in economic development has not been recognized and their status is very low. They don't have equal rights in their occupation and their choices are also limited to select an occupation due to cultural, social and economic constraints. Women face gender bias in the labour market as well. Especially in the unorganized sector the status of women is very pathetic and they also face various types of exploitation at work. Gender inequality in the agriculture sector is a serious issue. Women have fewer basic facilities like health, employment, and education as compared to men. Although women are the largest producers of food grains, they get less food and

nutrition as compared to men. They are not given equal wages as men for the same work. It is that the productivity of female workers is lower than that of males, hence women are entitled to lower wages. In reality, women farmers are contributing equally or even more to the production as men. Even today in our country, women workers are not given equal rights as male workers. The problem of gender discrimination against workers is not only a problem of India, it is a serious problem of all developed and underdeveloped countries. According to the Global Gender Gap Index 2022, India ranks 135th among 146 countries.

Objective of study The objective of this research paper is to analyse the role of women in the agriculture sector and gender-based biases faced by women in the agriculture sector.

Review of Literature

Jamali (2009) examined that women play an important role in the agriculture sector in Pakistan and perform major duties in the agriculture sector. Despite their duties, they are discriminated against in decision-making. They don't have the choice to select an occupation according to their desire due to various social and cultural constraints.

Roshan Lal and Ashok Khurana (2011) in their paper titled "Gender issues: the role of women in the agriculture sector" have analyzed the role of women, and gender disparities in the agricultural sector and also suggested ways and means to improve the status of women in this sector. Women do not have much access to resources such as animals, land, and machinery. Women are also not having decision-making rights whether outside or at home. They are paid less wages as compared to men for the same work. Women face a high degree of discrimination in almost all spheres of the agriculture sector.

Jayasheela G. (2015) in her paper "The Role of Women: In Indian Agriculture Sector" has expressed the role of women in the agriculture sector. The agriculture sector creates many jobs for women but there is a difference in wages earned by women and men. Women perform physically hard duties but women's labour power is considered inferior to men.

Manesh Rani et. all (2019) Found that women play an important role in the agriculture sector in crop production, livestock production, horticulture, post-harvesting operations, forestry fishing, etc. Animal husbandries depend heavily on women. But still, the position of women in the agriculture sector is insignificant. Women face gender bias in the male-dominated agriculture sector. Lack of awareness and lower access to modern technology is a big challenge for women.

Rakesh et. al in an article namely "role of women in Indian agriculture" (2022) have highlighted the role of women in various agriculture activities, such as dairy farming sericulture and fisheries, horticulture and food security, nutrition and allied sector. According to them, women have an important role in agriculture.

Abdisa et al. (2024) Found that the gender disparity in agricultural output in Ethiopia, dissecting the ways in which gender-based inequalities in knowledge, technology, and resources lead to lower yields from male farmers compared to their female counterparts. Baysan et al. (2024) investigated their research on rural communities' agricultural wage disparity, which was published in the Journal of Development Economics. The research highlights the need of implementing policies and initiatives for wage equality.

Methodology This paper is based on secondary data. Secondary data is collected from books, journals NSSO, population census 2011, and agriculture census.

Analysis

Contribution of women in the agriculture sector –

The role of women in the agriculture sector is intangible. Women play a multidimensional role and perform numerous jobs ranging from fetching water from far to weeding, hoeing, cutting and collecting fodder for animals, picking and separating seeds from fibre, collecting wood for fuel, looking after livestock, pole try, harvesting, loading and unloading of products, storing products, packing of products, cotton picking, depends upon women. Women perform hard duties as compared to men at home or farm. Based on the following data of NSSO, it is analyzed that women's contribution in the agriculture sector is more than men's.

The estimated percentage distribution of workers in Agriculture

Annual Periodic Labour Force Survey report year	Male percentage	Female percentage	Person percentage
PLFS (2020-21)	39.8	62.2	46.5

PLFS (2021-22)	38.1	62.9	45.5
PLFS (2022-23)	37.1	64.3	45.8

Source: Annual Periodic Labour Force Survey report 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23

Note: Broad Industrial division as per National Industrial Classification (2008)

According to the NSSO annual periodic labour force survey for 2022-2023 (July June) percentage distribution of persons in agriculture is 45.8 percent, the estimated percentage distribution of male workers in agriculture is 37.1 percent and female workers is 64.3 percent.

Gender-based Biasness in the Agriculture sector:

1. Women are paid less wages than men for the same work. Women are contributing equally to the production as men but they do not get equal pay even for equal work. Landlords pre assume that the productivity of female workers is lower than that of males, hence women are entitled to lower wages. The Equal Wage Act is not working properly in the unorganized agriculture sector.
2. There is Inequality regarding basic facilities at the workplace. Male workers are provided with more basic facilities such as washrooms, water, medical etc. in comparison to female workers.
3. Gender inequality is prevalent in skill and vocational training, as well in the majority of cases men, are the only beneficiaries of these training.
4. There is inequality in employment opportunities. In the majority of countries, women get fewer opportunities in employment despite being equally or sometimes even more qualified than men.
5. Ownership of women in household assets or land holdings is very negligible. Generally, women are not given ownership rights either in assets or land. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Globally, male landlords are 85 percent and female landlords are less than 15 percent of the total. There is a lack of awareness among women regarding their legal property rights. Some women are aware of their property rights but due to social and cultural constraints, they do not claim their rights.
6. Women are not economically independent, because women stay behind at home to look after the household and children and men go out to earn. Those women who go out to earn, do not have the right to use their earnings without the permission of the head of the family. As such women are economically dependent on men.

Suggestions:

These are the following recommendations to reduce gender discrimination and for recognition the role of women in the agriculture sector:

1. To increase the access of women to Kisan credit cards, there must be a low interest rate on Kisan credit cards for women in comparison to men.
2. To reduce gender inequality in the agriculture sector, there is a need to give more decision-making power to women in the sale and purchase of cattle and machinery, the sale of agriculture production, and selecting seeds and crop patterns.
3. To prevent gender exploitation women's literacy is very must. The lack of literacy among women is a major cause of gender exploitation. Illiterate women are not aware
4. of their rights. There is a big literacy gap between men and women, this gap must be filled. Educated women are the need of the hour.
5. There is a need to run an awareness programme for females, to increase women awareness related to their rights of equal wages, property rights, and other rights.
6. There is a need for strict implementation of gender exploitation prevention acts.
7. There is an assumption of employers that women's productivity is low as compared to men, so employers pay less wage to women labourers as compared to men for the same work. This assumption of landlords is not true. Society or landlords need to change their thinking about women's labour productivity and the government should run a training and skill programme under the Skill India Mission to train women labour for agricultural activities.

Conclusion Women play a significant role in the agriculture sector and are the major contributor to the economy. Although women are an integral part of agricultural labour, they face gender discrimination in the agriculture sector as well as at home. It has been evident that although women are the major producers of food yet they eat less food, have fewer land rights in comparison to men and are discriminated against with lower wages, low literacy rates, low basic facilities at the workplace and self-employment in the form of unpaid

workers. A labour-intensive country like India can develop at a rapid pace by preventing gender discrimination and making efficient use of women. Government must formulate policies to improve the condition of women in the agriculture sector and there is also a need to reform the existing laws and schemes running for the welfare of women. Women are less aware of their rights and schemes running for their welfare, so the government also takes initiative for the women's awareness. There is an urgent need to implement government policies at the ground level.

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